

Review on Botanical & Pharmacological Properties of *Guilandina bonduc* L

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ABSTRACT

Botanical characteristics and pharmacological properties of *Guilandina bonduc* L., highlighting its traditional uses and scientifically validated activities. It describes the morphology, habitat, taxonomy, and ethnomedicinal applications of the plant, including its use in treating fevers, gynecological disorders, and skin diseases. The pharmacological investigations focus on the plant's antioxidant, antimicrobial, antimalarial, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, antifertility, anticancer, and other bioactivities, which are backed by a number of in vitro and in vivo studies. The phytochemicals responsible for these effects, including flavonoids, saponins, phenolics, and terpenoids, are also discussed, highlighting the plant's potential as a source of bioactive compounds for drug development. Overall, the review consolidates existing knowledge and emphasizes the therapeutic potential of *Guilandina bonduc* L. in modern medicine.

Keywords: - antitumor, antioxidant, antimicrobial, antidiabetic, anti-inflammatory, antifertility, antimalarial, abortifacient, ant spermatogenic.

INTRODUCTION

People have utilized medicinal plants, and for a very long time, accurate records of their use were maintained (Petrovska, 2012). Natural plant products have been separated in the present era for the purpose of developing new drugs. Secondary plant product analysis has advanced significantly over the past 20 to 30 years (Okada et al., 2010). Because they are beneficial to both humans and animals, medicinal plants are becoming more and more important in healthcare systems around the world. They are prized for their ability to improve general health as well as their function in curing illnesses. However, determining the precise components in charge of their healing qualities is crucial to maximizing their therapeutic potential (Sofowora et al., 2013). The plant parts of *Guilandina bonduc* L. have been used historically as a vesicant, periodic, antipyretic, and tonic for the treatment of gynecological disorders, skin diseases, constipation, piles, ulcers, rheumatism, and backache. Various extracts of *C. crista* have been found to have cytotoxic activity, antioxidant activity, antimalarial activity (Bodakhe et al., 2011, Mandal et al., 2011).

Botanical description

Guilandina bonduc (*Caesalpinia bonduc*) commonly known as grey nicker, nicker bean, or knicker nut, is a species of flowering plant in the senna tribe, belongs to the family Fabaceae. It can be found in the Himalayas, wastelands all throughout India, and the delta areas of western, eastern, and southern India at elevations of up to 1000 meters above sea level. Additionally, it thrives mostly in India's

tropical regions, particularly in moist deciduous and evergreen woods. In agricultural areas, this species is also cultivated as a fence plant (Watson & Fowden, 1973). *Guilandina bonduc* L. can grow as a liana or a climbing shrub. It bears thorns on its stems and leaf stalks and can reach a height of 8 meters. The leaves are 50 cm long, pinnate, bipinnate, and come in four to five pairs. There are five to eight leaflets on the petiole. The form of the leaves was either elliptical or oblong. The bases of leaves were rounded. The leaves have mucronate and obtuse apices. The length of the longest petioles is 56.1 cm long. Stipules are present in it. The flowers are yellow in colour, racemes that might be simple or branching. August through December was the following time frame. The oblong-ovate fruits have dense spines, beaked tips, and infected pods; hemisphere-shaped and glossy are seeds 1 or 2, In October, fruiting starts (Khare, 2008).

Taxonomic position

Kingdom: Plantae

Clade: Magnoliophyta

Clade: Magnoliopsida

Clade: Angiospermae

Order: Fabales

Family: Fabaceae/Caesalpinaceae

Genus: *Guilandina*

Species: *bonduc*

Binomial name: *Guilandina bonduc* (L.) Roxb.

Pharmacological Properties

Since 1932, the herb has been used traditionally. It offers a broad spectrum of therapeutic possibilities, per earlier research. In traditional medicine, several portions of this plant are used to cure a variety of illnesses either by themselves or in combination with other medicinal plants as polyherbs. *Guilandina bonduc* L. recorded several pharmacological properties. This segment deals with the detailed pharmacological properties of *Guilandina bonduc* L.

Antitumor properties

This study examined the anticancer potential of methanolic extracts of *Guilandina bonduc* L. (MECB) leaves against Ehrlich Ascites Carcinoma (EAC). Over the course of 14 days following tumor inoculation, the extract was given at doses of 50, 100, and 200 mg/kg/day. The findings indicate that MECB improved survival rates while greatly lowering tumor volume, packed cell volume, and viable cell count. Normal hematological and biochemical parameters, as well as enhanced antioxidant status, were demonstrated by treated mice. At test levels, no discernible toxicity was seen; however, at 300 mg/kg, toxicity was evident. MECB offers significant anticancer potential with little short-term toxicity, according to the study's findings (Gupta et al., 2004). Sandhia and Bindu used the Trypan blue exclusion method to assess the cytotoxic and anti-inflammatory effects of *Guilandina bonduc* L. stem bark extract on carrageenan-induced rat paw edema and Daltons Ascites Lymphoma (DLA) cells. The extract demonstrated 100% cytotoxicity at 100 µg/mL and dose-dependent anti-inflammatory

efficacy when evaluated at doses ranging from 10 to 200 $\mu\text{g/mL}$. High concentrations of phenolic and flavonoid chemicals were found by phytochemical analysis; these compounds are probably what cause the biological activities that have been reported. The study emphasizes how *Guilandina bonduc* L. stem bark may comprise anti-inflammatory and anti-cancer compounds (Sandhia & Bindu, 2015).

Antioxidant properties

The antioxidant activity of the chloroform extract of *Guilandina bonduc* L. seeds was examined by Kumar et al. They showed significant antioxidant capacity using the β -carotene bleaching test, the DPPH free radical scavenging experiment, and the measurement of total phenolic content. In comparison to conventional BHA, which had an IC_{50} value of 46.70 ± 0.43 , the extract had an IC_{50} value of $170 \pm 4.08 \mu\text{g/mL}$, a total phenolic content of 21.96 ± 2.12 (at $1000 \mu\text{g/mL}$), and an investigation of antioxidant activity of 24.96 ± 0.31 . These findings imply that *Guilandina bonduc* L. seed chloroform extract has strong antioxidant qualities, most likely as a result of its phenolic content (Sachan et al., 2010). *Guilandina bonduc* L. seed ethanolic extract was found to have excellent antioxidant activity by Shukla et al. (2009). With an IC_{50} of $74.73 \mu\text{g/mL}$, the extract demonstrated dose-dependent DPPH scavenging. Additionally, it successfully inhibited hydroxyl, nitric oxide, and superoxide radicals. Contrast to regular gallic acid, the total phenolic concentration was greater. These findings imply that *Guilandina bonduc* L. seeds possess strong antioxidant qualities. The phytochemicals and antioxidant activity of *Guilandina bonduc* L. root, stem, leaves, and seed kernel ethanol extracts were studied by Sembiring et al. While flavonoids and saponins were present in all parts, the largest concentrations of phenolics and flavonoids were found in the leaves. The leaf extract had the highest antioxidant activity, as determined by the DPPH experiment. The order of effectiveness was leaf > root > stem > seed kernel (Sembiring et al., 2018).

Antidiabetic properties

The antidiabetic properties of *Guilandina bonduc* L. seed kernel preparations, which have long been utilized in traditional medicine, were documented by Parameshwer in diabetic rats, polar extracts (ethyl acetate and aqueous) significantly reduced blood sugar levels and raised liver glycogen and fat levels. Petroleum ether showed no action, while non-polar extracts showed less. Triterpenoidal glycosides are responsible for the antidiabetic action, and ethyl acetate extract demonstrated significant antioxidant activity as well (Parameshwar et al., 2002). In studies of glucose sufferance in both normal and diabetic rats, Patil et al. showed that extracts from the bark and roots of *Guilandina bonduc* L. had antidiabetic properties. Blood glucose levels were considerably lowered by aqueous ethanol and chloroform extracts; the strongest effect was observed at 250 mg/kg after three hours. After long-term treatment, both extracts demonstrated better glucose, lipid, and urea profiles along with more than 22% protection. They were just as effective as the common medication glibenclamide (Patil et al., 2011). In rats with alloxan-induced hyperglycemia, a study on *Guilandina bonduc* L. seed extracts revealed notable antidiabetic benefits. Blood urea/nitrogen and blood glucose levels were decreased by oral treatment at 300 mg/kg . By reducing LDL and cholesterol, the extract also alleviated hyperlipidemia brought on by diabetes. It may have high antidiabetic and antihyperlipidemic potential because it inhibits the absorption of glucose (Kannur et al., 2006).

Anti-inflammatory properties

Arunadevi demonstrated that *Guilandina bonduc* L. flower extract (CBFE) significantly reduced inflammation in various models, including carrageenan-induced edema and chronic granuloma. At 300 mg/kg, CBFE also lowered arthritis severity and radiographic scores, confirming its strong anti-inflammatory properties (Arunadevi et al., 2015). *Guilandina bonduc* L. seed extracts, 30 and 40 μ L, both aqueous and aqua-alcoholic extracts exhibited anti-inflammatory effect; however, diclofenac showed a greater inhibition at a concentration of 50 μ L (Sasidharan et al., 2021).

Antifertility properties

The antifertility effect of *Guilandina bonduc* L. ethanolic seed extract was explored in female rats. The study found that the extract's antiprogestosterone activity is responsible for the antifertility effect, as treated rats exhibited decreased progesterone levels, increased resorption, and decreased implantation rates, as well as corpora lutea deterioration and embryonic abnormalities (Ahmed, 2013).

Antibacterial properties

Simin evaluated the antibacterial and antifungal activities of *Guilandina bonduc* L. seed extracts and the isolated compound bondenolide. They tested the methanol extract, ethyl acetate fraction, and water-soluble methanol extract for antimicrobial effects, along with assessing phytotoxicity (Simin et al., 2001). Arif describes both in-vitro and in-vivo antibacterial activities of *Guilandina bonduc* L. seeds, confirming their potential as effective antimicrobial agents (Arif et al., 2009). A chemical called (2-hydroxy-2-methylpropyl)—(2-hydroxy-3-methylbut-2-en-1-yl) polymethylene that was isolated from *Caesalpinia bonduc* was found to have antibacterial action (Sagar et al. 2010).

Antimalarial properties

From *Guilandina bonduc* L. seed kernels, Pudhom extracted three novel cassane furanoditerpenoids and assessed their antimalarial properties. These substances showed encouraging efficacy against the *Plasmodium falciparum* K1 strain, which is resistant to multiple drugs (Pudhom et al., 2007). *Guilandina bonduc* L. cassane and norcassane diterpenes have been shown to have antimalarial properties by Kalauni. Additionally, they investigated the connection between these compounds' chemical structures and antimalarial efficacy (Kalauni et al., 2006). *Guilandina bonduc* L. in Indonesia yielded cassane and norcassane diterpenes, which Linn isolated and showed to have antimalarial properties against *Plasmodium falciparum* (Linn et al., 2005).

Abortifacient properties

In rural India, *Guilandina bonduc* L. seeds have long been used to control female fertility, while the leaves are used to facilitate birthing. The plant's abortifacient qualities are demonstrated by the fact that a combination of sesame oil and seed powder can cause abortion (Lilaram, & Raichur, 2014).

Antispermatic properties

The antispermatic properties of *Guilandina bonduc* L. seed extract was investigated in male albino rats by Kanerkar et al. (2015). Sperm density and count were significantly reduced after 21 days of

oral treatment of the aqueous extract. At doses of 50, 100, and 150 mg/kg, the extract's antispermato-genic activity increased, demonstrating a dose-dependent impact. At the highest dose, the maximum inhibition was 39.79 percent. These findings point to the possibility of using *Guilandina bonduc* L. seeds as a method of male contraception (Kanerkar et al., 2015).

CONCLUSION

Numerous pharmacological actions, including as antioxidant, antibacterial, antimalarial, anti-inflammatory, antidiabetic, antifertility, and anticancer qualities, are possessed by *Guilandina bonduc* L. Its abundant phytochemical components, including flavonoids, saponins, phenolics, and terpenoids, are primarily responsible for these activities. Scientific research backs up the plant's traditional medical applications and suggests that it could be a useful source of bioactive chemicals for creating novel therapeutic medicines. To fully utilize its therapeutic potential, more research is required to completely comprehend its modes of action, safety profile, and clinical efficacy. All things considered, *Guilandina bonduc* L. is still a viable option for pharmacological and medicinal research in the future.

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